

OVERCOMING CHALLENGES IN INCLUSIVE EDUCATION: SUCCESS STORIES OF RECEIVING TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

Challenges in inclusive education are still a pressing issue that many schools deal with. Teachers are doing the best they can to provide the education their students with special needs require despite their tough situations. Hence, this study mainly aims to explore the experiences of receiving teachers in overcoming challenges encountered as they implement inclusive education despite the lack of formal training. This study employed a qualitative research design; particularly, a narrative approach and thematic analysis were utilized in analyzing the data. The findings of the study revealed that the teachers were able to overcome challenges in implementing inclusive education by consulting experienced teachers, seeking support from co-teachers, reinforcing through the Internet, giving extra care and attention to Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs), gathering support from parents, and utilizing personal resources. Despite having a lack of formal teacher training in inclusive education, receiving regular teachers were able to surpass the varied challenges they encountered successfully but still strongly recommend the provision of formal and effective teacher training to become well-equipped and competent in handling a diverse group of learners in a regular classroom setting.

Keywords: *inclusive education, overcoming challenges in inclusive education, success stories in inclusive education, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

For years, inclusion has been one of the major turning points of educational reforms in the special education system around the globe. Inclusive education is when all learners, regardless of any disabilities they may have, are placed in age-appropriate general education classes to receive high-quality instruction, interventions, and support (Alquraini & Gut, 2012). Regular education teachers, the ones given the most crucial responsibility of putting inclusive practices into action, however, still continue to indicate that they feel inadequately equipped to take the responsibility of educating diverse learners in an inclusive setting. It is evident in the study of Muega and Echavia (2011) that a number of participants, most regular education teachers, have expressed concern over their lack of inclusive education training. The lack of knowledge of inclusion is revealed to be a cause of negative attitudes, thus acting as a barrier to its success in schools.

Several existing federal legislations around the world mandate that Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) are required to receive their education within an environment. Teachers, as well, should be provided with sufficient training and support to make themselves equipped with the skills and expertise before they can handle learners with special needs in an inclusive setting. In the United States of America, the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA 2004) and the Special Education Needs and Disability Act of 2001 in the United Kingdom continue to provide adequate educational support to learners with special needs, including the assertive provision of any forms of support to teachers including teacher training.

In the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) advocates the fundamental principle of inclusive schooling that all children should learn together, whenever possible, regardless of their difficulties or differences. Under the management of the Special Education Division of the Bureau of Elementary Education (BEE), the ultimate goal of special education is integrating or mainstreaming learners with special needs into the regular school system and ultimately in the community.

This move by DepEd is in accordance with the United Nations Education Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) as stipulated in the UNESCO Tool Kit-Book I on Inclusive Education. The toolkit offers a holistic and practical guide on how classrooms can be more inclusive and learning-friendly by assessing the school's inclusive practices in the following areas: school policies and administrative support, school environment, teacher skills, knowledge and attitudes, teacher development, pupils, academic content and assessment, special subject areas/extra-curricular activities and community. Upon their acceptance of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs), Filipino teachers embrace this principle in recognition of its vital role in providing basic quality education for all.

In 2008, former Department of Education Secretary Jesli Lopus presented a report at the United Nations Convention in Geneva, Switzerland, about the status of the Philippine Education System, including inclusive education for special children. In his

statement, he expounded that the department provides opportunities for continuous upgrading of teachers' professional competencies through self-instructional learning modules.

Unfortunately, regular Filipino education teachers in the actual field experience the opposite plight. Findings conducted by Yap and Adorio (2008) show that the competence of teachers appeared to be one of the major problems in promoting special education in public schools due to inadequate information or lack of training of teachers. The study also affirms that many regular teachers were not knowledgeable of Special Education (SpEd) programs, including the formulation of Individualized Education Programs (IEP) among others.

In Davao City, Philippines, a study by Gomez (2012) in a particular school clearly pointed out that regular education teachers and most school personnel are generally not trained to address concerns about students with special needs. Teachers are also uninformed ahead of time that they have students with disabilities in their class lists. Since they are aware of the "zero rejection" policy in schools, they are left with no option but to accept learners with special needs in their classes without any knowledge about them and their conditions. Thus, many teachers do not have any inkling on how to handle learners with special needs inside and outside the classroom.

As recommended, Gomez emphasized that issues and concerns relative to the implementation of inclusive education can be successfully implemented by hearing the sentiments of the teachers and those students with special needs.

Another study was conducted by Casquejo and Vitto (2019) on the views of selected kindergarten teachers implementing inclusive education in identified public schools in Matina District, Davao City, Philippines. Results conclude that most kindergarten teachers remain unaware and unequipped for the effective implementation of inclusion. It also concludes that the inclusion caused the kindergarten teachers distress, frustration, exhaustion, and disappointment. If these are not addressed in a timely manner, holistically and scientifically, the supposed Kindergarten teachers will remain unequipped and unprepared, thus affecting the Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSENs). to be given the proper education that they deserve. However, the respondents and the researcher remain hopeful that they will be given the support and training for inclusive education, which will make the LSENs more competent to face the community or even the workforce.

It is in these premises that the researcher purposely conducted this study in order to recognize the important roles of teachers in shaping the realization of inclusive education in the classrooms. The researcher in school actually observes the occurrence of this problem. This study will particularly focus on investigating how non-trained teachers implement inclusive education and how they overcome the challenges they experience in handling learners with special needs despite their lack of inclusive education training. Ultimately, the main phenomena will reveal the success cases of these teachers. Although a bunch of research focuses on the different challenges of teachers in inclusive education, little research has focused on overcoming the

challenges they continually face as they apply inclusive education to full actualization inside their regular classrooms.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This study aimed to explore the experiences of regular teachers in implementing inclusive education in a sole Special Education school in Baguio District, Davao City Philippines. It aimed to have an in-depth description of the challenges encountered by regular teachers in teaching learners with special needs (LSEs) in their regular class, how they cope, and how they overcome these challenges. Ultimately, it sought to go deep into the stories of the success of these regular teachers. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following research questions:

1. How do regular teachers implement inclusive education?
2. How do regular teachers overcome challenges in the beginning, middle, and present?
3. How do they appreciate the successful cases?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a qualitative research design; mainly, a narrative approach and thematic analysis were utilized in analyzing the data. The narrative approach was employed in this study in order to tell the stories of six regular education teachers through their individual lives and write narratives of their experiences in overcoming challenges in inclusive education despite their lack of inclusive education training. It was also emphasized in this study their success stories of how they were able to surpass the challenges they faced in implementing inclusive education. The key informants of the study were the six licensed professional teachers of a sole Special Education school in Baguio District, Davao City, Philippines that caters to Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs). They were selected as participants through purposive sampling.

The research instrument utilized in this study is a researcher-constructed interview guide. The interview guide enabled the researcher to gather information from the participants. The interview guide comprised of two parts: Part 1, involved the demographic profile of the regular teachers handling Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) in their regular class. Part 2 was composed of interview questions that sought to answer the purpose of this study.

In analyzing the data, the researcher utilized thematic analysis. This study focused on themes and codes. The six phases of thematic analysis by Braun and Clarke (2006) were followed in this study and applied systematically. This study also underwent the appropriate research procedure and proper ethical protocols to ensure that the participants were kept completely anonymous in the research, and the interviews were held confidential to maintain the objectivity of the study and to keep the identities of the participants of this study completely anonymous thus maintaining their rights.

This study utilized a non-probability sample that was selected based on the population's characteristics and the study's objective. Purposive sampling is also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. Hence, this study only applies to qualified samples based on the criteria needed for the study. There are only a few key informants since this study is particular to the qualifying criteria.

RESULTS

Based on the data analysis, the study concluded with three primary themes: implementation of inclusive education, overcoming challenges in inclusive education, and success stories. Moreover, the study revealed the overarching themes of each primary theme. The overarching themes are explored through discussions based on the accounts of the key informants of this study.

Implementation of Inclusive Education

Figure 1. Thematic map showing the main theme 'Implementation of Inclusive Education' and associated subthemes

Overcoming Challenges in Inclusive Education

Figure 3: Final thematic map showing the main theme 'Overcoming Challenges in Inclusive Education' and associated subthemes.

Success Stories

Figure 4: Final thematic map showing the main theme 'Success Stories' and associated subthemes.

DISCUSSIONS

Inclusive education is always been a pressing concern not just in the Philippines, but in other parts of the world as well. This issue should be appropriately addressed by providing an adequate school system that accommodates the necessities of students with special needs. Teachers play crucial roles in implementing inclusive education since they directly interact with students. Hence, in this study, the teachers' roles and experiences are explored to shed light on some situations in handling inclusive education.

Implementation of Inclusive Education

In the pursuit of taking the task of educating diverse learners in an inclusive setting and performing their most crucial responsibility of making inclusive practices into action, key informants revealed their way of implementing inclusive education despite the lack of formal training. Responses involve their way of implementing inclusive education based on the following themes: mixture of diverse learners, training, contextualization of lessons, activities and strategies, and challenges.

Mixture of Diverse Learners. The response of key informants in terms of how they teach in a classroom setting with learners with special needs and regular learners at the same time revealed that they taught the day's lesson to the whole class as one with the learners with special needs and the regular learners. This kind of setting was common to most responses of participants.

“Sa akong klase, ginadungan nako siya sa akong regular learners’ kay makablend man siya sa ilaha.” (“In my class, I let him join with regular learners because he can blend with them.”), KI-1

“Ginadungan nako siya sa uban pag magdiscuss na sa lesson. Dili siya ginalah maski pa sa iyang condition nga hina siya ug pagsabot.” (“I joined him with others during discussion of the lesson. I did not isolate him with others despite his condition of being slow in comprehension”), KI-3

“Ang akong style sa teaching-learning instruction, ginasabay jud nako siya sa mga regular, dungan gud ug group activities pati sa pagdeliver sa lesson sabay.” (“My style during teaching learning instruction was I included him together with my regular learners during group activities and even during delivering the lesson.”), KI-4

“Una, maghatag ko’g instruction nila tanan sabay, pati pagtudlo sa lesson sabay.” (“First, I gave them the instruction together and teaching the lesson at the same time”), KI-5

“While nagatudlo ko sa regular, siya naa siya sa likod tapad sa akong lamesa, tagaan nako siya activity. First to second grading na. Pagka third grading, giapil na nako siya sa group.” (“While I teach the regular learners, he was seated at the back near my table, I provided him with activity. That was from first to second grading. During the third grading, I let him join with the group.”), KI-2

On the contrary, key informants attested that they isolated the LSEs from the group in terms of activity sheets or worksheets that catered the particular need of the learners.

“Naa siya’y worksheet nga iyaha lang, dili pareha sa worksheet sa regular, para sa iyaha lang” (“He has his own worksheet for him alone, not like of the regular learners, it was only for him.”), KI-3

“Paghuman sa klase, ginatagaan nako siya ug lahi nga activity sheets.” (“After classes, I gave him differentiated activity sheets”), KI-6

As Salend (2005) defined inclusion principle, it is when all learners regardless of disabilities they may, are placed in regular education classes together with regular learners to receive high quality instruction, intervention and support. Clearly, informants’ set-up of mixing diverse learners in one classroom setting corroborated the inclusion principle as defined.

Despite their seemed familiarity with inclusive education, the participants expressed doubts regarding their conceptions and practice of it. This ambiguity embedded from their lack of knowledge and trainings in teaching inclusive education.

This is not a startling observation since they are not required to undergo a series of compulsory and mandatory inclusive education trainings before they will receive mainstreamed Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) in their regular class. Therefore, in order to take the responsibility positively, regular teachers implemented

inclusion in its basic sense that is mixing diverse group of learners in one classroom setting.

Similarly, Forlin, Earle, Loreman, and Sharma (2011) emphasize in their study on preparing pre-service teachers that “preparing teachers in inclusive schools requires universities and colleges to ensure that their curriculum covers sufficient detail to enable newly-receiving teachers to cater for the increasing diversity of student needs.” Much is true for in-service teachers who have no background.

Contextualization of Lessons, Activities and Strategies. Inclusive Education (IE), in its very sense, aims to ensure that diverse learners are accorded equal rights and opportunities in education. It does not have one sole definition or method of implementation to suit all individuals and situations. It stresses more on evolving inclusive practices which can be adapted in various contexts.

Having insufficient prior knowledge about implementing the inclusion curriculum, key informants shared how they implemented inclusion in their own context. As revealed, contextualizing the curriculum for the teaching and learning activities in an inclusive setting was their way of implementing inclusion. Despite the lack of training and orientation in implementing inclusive education in the regular class, key informants conducted classroom activities in their own contextualized way in order to ensure the provision of good, if not quality, form of education for LSEs.

Faced with different unfamiliar cases and severity, regular teachers contextualize teaching strategies that address the individual needs of their LSEs. To develop the socialization skills of the LSE, group activities and practical training proved to be effective for the teacher. One informant shared:

“Para mdevelop iyang socialization, nagagroupings ko. Ginapastorya nako siya sa regular magdrawing sila ug magcolor-color sila. Ginatrain pud nako siya ug mga gaan lang nga sugo.” (“To develop socialization, I do groupings. I let him talk with regular peers while drawing and coloring. Then I also trained to perform manageable errands.”), KI-1

Key informants who had learners with Learning Disability (LD), catered their needs making use of their own contextualized strategies. Key informant 2 explained her style in teaching:

“Sa reading niya sa Filipino, ginapafamiliarize nako sa iyaha basta naay A pareha sa ba, ihap siya’g 1, kung e pareha sa be, kay 2, kung i, bi, ihap ug 3. Kanang ana ra gud.” (“In reading Filipino words, I let him familiarize, if the word has ‘a’ as in ‘ba,’ count 1, with ‘e’ as in ‘be,’ count 2, with ‘i’ as in ‘bi,’ count 3. As simple as that”), KI-2

Key informants 4, 5 and 6 utilized manipulative materials as effective learning aids in conducting remedial instruction to their learners with Learning Disability (LD). They explained respectively:

“Ginatagaan nako siya ug flashcards nga siya lang. Unya, akong checkan iyang trabaho.” (“I gave him flashcards on his own. Then, he will let me check his work.”), KI-5

“Nakarealize ko nga dapat manipulate gyud. Pareho sa paggunit ug balas”. (“I realized that the child should manipulate things like using sand.”), KI-5

“Naa koy mga letter patterns, ginapatrace nako siya. Unya, mugamit pud ko ug graphic organizer para sa sayon lang nga story unya pangutan-on nako siya paghuman.” (“I have letter patterns, I let him trace the letter. Then, I also use graphic organizers for simple stories and asked him questions after.”), KI-6

For most participants, they claimed that the strategies and activities they employed were much effective even if they had not undergone formal inclusive education trainings.

Dakar and Senegal (2000) stressed that IE does not have one single definition or method of implementation. It stresses more on evolving inclusive practices which can be adapted in various contexts. Key informants’ differentiated ways of conceptualizing lessons, activities and strategies only suited well inclusion’s goals of enhancing LSENS’ participation, promoting child-centered approaches to teaching and learning and minimizing exclusion, in a manner that successfully addressed the diverse needs of all learners. In this set-up, education is also accessible without discrimination. Informants’ accounts clearly viewed that they are on the right track of implementing inclusion practices. Additionally, Salend (2005) suggested that effective inclusive educators are expected to differentiate their teaching methods and techniques to meet individual needs and strengths.

Challenges Encountered. As key informants struggle to implement inclusive education, they experienced varied challenges. They shared their most common challenges in implementing the inclusion curriculum particularly in the classroom management. Since there is no clear and definite guide for teachers to be followed in this multifaceted classroom set-up, teachers felt the different forms of challenges. Challenges encountered involves in key informants’ knowledge, attitude, resources, parent support and administrative support.

Training. In this study, participants were asked about the number of the trainings in inclusive education they attended and how these trainings support the adequacy of their knowledge in handling learners in an inclusive setting. Identically, Key Informants responded to the questions in terms of number of trainings in inclusive education they had attended and courses taken part in teaching Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSENS).

The Key informants commonly shared that they had not attended any inclusive education teacher trainings and seminars in the different levels: school, district and division. Neither have they taken part in any courses in teaching learners with special needs. Key informants resounded the same answer that for a year of accepting and dealing with LSENs in their regular class, they were not able to undergo any trainings and seminars about inclusive education provided for them in school, district and even in the division level.

“Wala ko kaattend ug training sa school Ma’am. Sa district, wala. Wala pud sa division, Ma’am.” (“I have not attended training in school Ma’am. In the district, none. There is also none in the division, Ma’am”), KI-1

“Trainings sa school? Wala ma’am. Sa district ug division, wala pud Ma’am. (“Trainings in school? None ma’am. In the district and division, there is also none Ma’am”), KI-2

Sa school Ma’am, wala man. District? Wala Ma’am. Sa division, wala” (“In school Ma’am, there was none. District? none Ma’am. In the division, none.”), KI-4

“Wala man sa school. Wala pud a district. Division Ma’am, wala.” (“Nothing in school. Nothing also in the district. Division Ma’am none.”), KI 6

These accounts of key informants manifested the lack of provision of trainings in inclusive education before they are given the task of practicing inclusion. Prior to the acceptance of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSENs) in their regular class, key informants were not given the opportunities to prepare and equip themselves with the knowledge and the expertise in handling an inclusive learning environment with varied and diverse group of learners.

Since key informants could tell the inadequacy of formal inclusive education trainings they have attended, evidence affirmed that informants also considered themselves inadequately knowledgeable and less competent in handling this kind of learners in an inclusive setting. This was confirmed by the similar answers of the participants that quoted:

“Kulang jud. Basi nana pud imainstream basi lahi na pud nga case. Kanang mga down syndrome, wala pako katesting basi imainstream ba. Unsaon na lang paghandle anang uban. Okay ra ng mga mild lang. Pero kanang mga lisod unsaon na lang paghandle ana nila kay wala man ko kaagi ug naa bay training para ana nila.” (“Really not enough. Another LSEN may be mainstreamed and the case may be more difficult to handle. Just like the down syndrome, I was not able to handle them yet. How am I going to handle this kind of learner? Mild cases are okay. But with complicated ones, it would be so difficult for me to handle them because I do not have any trainings intended for them”), KI- 1

“Wala ko’y trainings naatenan so wala kaayo’y makatabang sa akong kabalo unsaon paghandle ang inclusive education especially sa mga special children.” (“I have no trainings attended so it would not suffice my knowledge in handling in inclusive education especially with special children.”), KI-2

The common answers of participants clearly showed that lack of teacher training in inclusive education posed as a big challenge for regular teachers in implementing inclusive education.

Rivkin, Hanushek, and Kain (2000) suggested in their study, that as teachers who cater LSEs in a mainstream school, one must undergo an in-service training organized by his/her local education authority to boost their experience. This may be because students are known to learn more from experienced teachers than they do from less experienced teachers. This also suggests that teachers with more teaching experience teach in a more effective way than those who are less experienced.

The key informants stated their knowledge of inclusive education with the awareness that it requires extra effort to succeed and that inclusion goes beyond the scope of general education that includes only students without special needs. Though supportive of inclusive education, the participants spoke of it with the admission that they are lacking in basic knowledge about their claimed inclusive practices. They believe that they practice inclusive education, but they are not quite certain whether the conceptual basis of their practice is sufficient to meet the standards of high-level inclusion. These observations are further substantiated with verbatim citations of some participants’ answers during the one-on-one interviews. Participants commonly shared their sentiments about how hard it is to implement inclusive education without adequate trainings.

“Naglisod ko kay wala man gud ko’y idea unsa ning condition aning bataa. Maayo unta nakaagi ko’g training para nakaidea ko gamay” (“It was really hard for me since I do not have the idea about this child’s condition. It would have been better if I had undergone training so I can have even a little amount of idea”), KI-2

It was common to the participants to describe inclusive education as an activity requiring additional effort to attain its practitioners’ goals. Evidently, the participants’ accounts affirmed their difficulty in implementing inclusion practices since they do not have the background and foundation through adequate and sufficient number of formal and quality inclusive education trainings.

Findings of the study also align with the study by Casquijo and Vitto (2019) to untrained Kindergarten teachers. Results concluded that the views and experiences of kindergarten teachers with inclusive education will persistently be unfavorable if they remain to be unacquainted and untrained with inclusion in terms of assessment, different learning and behavioral disorders, strategies to manage children with special

needs and management of inclusive classroom. A call for support, dissemination and training for inclusive education is hoped to be enhanced.

Knowledge. One cannot practice what one does not know. Prior to regular teachers' first-time implementation of inclusion in their respective classrooms, they were asked to share their knowledge about their Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSENs). In this study, their knowledge about LSENs is associated with the awareness and the ability of the regular teachers to identify the case and condition of their LSENs thus having the competence to cater their needs in an inclusive classroom setting. The participants have similar responses regarding their knowledge and awareness about the condition of their LSENs. Three out of the six key informants forthrightly revealed that they were not fully aware about the conditions of their LSENs by the time they accepted them in regular class. This was shared by the participants when they said:

“Wala jud ko’y idea. Maski pag gibasa nako ang result sa iyang diagnosis, wala gihapon ko kakuha unsay pasabot ato.” (“I really do not have any idea. Even if I have read the result from his diagnosis, I still did not know the meaning behind it”), KI-2

“Honestly, dili ko aware sa condition sa bata. Kato lang nag end na jud ang school year nga gi fill-out nako ang LRN sa LIS kay kailangan man i-indicate ang condition sa bata. Nakaingon gud ko, aw ing-ani diay ni iyang case?” (“Honestly, I am not aware of the boy’s condition. Just during the end of the school year when I filled out the LRN in the LIS because it was compulsory to indicate the condition of the child. I have asked myself, this was his case means.”), KI-3

“Pagsugod jud, feeling nako di ko prepared kay wala man koy kabalo ani iyang batasan oi. Mao to naglisod ko unsaon pagmanage niya” (“In the beginning, I felt unprepared because I am unfamiliar of his behaviour. That’s why I have difficulty how to manage him.”), KI-4

Though they have limited knowledge about the condition of their LSENs, they never hesitated to accept the child because of the “no rejection” policy which they obediently followed. A participant shared:

“Wala ko’y idea aning iyang condition. Gidawat lang nako kay bawal man mudili.” (“I do not have any idea about the condition of the child. I just accepted him because it is unlawful to reject him”), KI-6

“Gidawat lang pud nako kay mao may kailangan.” (“I just accepted because that is what is needed.”), KI-3

The accounts of the key informants showed that they lack basic knowledge about the kind of condition of LSENs that they are handling with. They have no choice but to implement inclusion because they are bound by their profession to teach diverse learners. The accounts of teachers clearly gave emphasis in the study of Gomez (2012) about teachers left with no option but to accept LSENs in their class without any

knowledge about them and their conditions because of the “no rejection” policy with which they are obliged to obey.

Because of this difficulty, key Informant 5 also revealed the burden she experienced in conceptualizing more differentiated and innovative techniques to suit her LSENS’ needs since she had limited knowledge on the different techniques in teaching in an inclusive classroom setting and basically about her LSEN.

“Challenge sa akong unsaon pag improve sa iyang disability ug unsaing technique itudlo sa iyaha. Halimbawa, di na mutalab ang peer tutoring sa iyaha, challenge kaayo unsas pay gamiton nga technique, unsa pang mga pamaagi nga matudluan siya.” (“It was a challenge for me to improve his disability and what appropriate technique I am going to teach him. For example, if peer tutoring was already ineffective for him, it was a challenge to think of another technique, other strategies to teach him.”), KI-5

It is salient that the responses of the key informants about their knowledge with the condition of the Learner with Special Needs (LSEs) under their regular class clearly manifested the lack of basic knowledge of regular teachers about implementing and handling inclusion as one of the challenges of regular teachers. Key informants manifested in their responses;

“Pirti gyung lisuda kay wala gani ko kabalo unsaon na siya. Naglibog ko unsay buhaton niya. Sige kog naanalyse analyse unsa akong buhaton niya para magpuyo kay di man maapply sa iyaha ang activity sa uban. Unsaon kaha ni noh?” (“Very hard because I really did not know how to handle him. I felt doubtful what to do. I kept on analysing on what to do to make him stay in place because the activities for my regular learners were not suitable for him. What will I do?”), KI-3

“Lisod oi kay kailangan jud siya ug special attention, unya makigdungan pani akong mga regular magsaba ug magkagubot ang klase. (“It was difficult because special attention should be given to him, at the same time, my regular learners would also make noise and chaos in class.”), KI-2

Key informants accounts can be reflected in the overall response of participants in the study of Muega and Echavia (2011) that revealed the teachers’ unpreparedness in taking on the challenge of handling students with disorders or disabilities.

Curriculum is often unable to meet the needs of a wide range of different learners. In many contexts including inclusion, the curriculum is centrally designed and rigid, leaving little flexibility for local adaptations or for teachers to experiment and try out new approaches. The content might be distant to the reality in which the students live, and therefore inaccessible and not motivating. When it comes to barriers to inclusion the analysis implies very significant and profound factors that inhibit successful inclusion.

Attitude. Educators are the most significant human resource for advancing inclusive education. Their proficiency and outlook have a dramatic impact on the lives of learners who are different and who have learning challenges. Unfortunately, the teachers' competency and attitudes can be the most important constraints for inclusive education. Apart from lack of technical ability is the teachers' attitude. In this study, participants described their feelings, behaviors and attitude towards implementing inclusive education practices.

In her first-time encounter with an inclusive classroom setting, one teacher described in detail that a feeling of anger filled her because of her lack of knowledge about her learner. So, a teacher noted that:

"Honestly, kay wala man ko kabalo unsay buhaton, naglagot ko. Kay sige man ko balik-balik sa lesson para sa akong special child, gidungag pa sa akong mga regulat. Samot pa kay wala ko'y idea. Mao to naglagot ko ani nga setting.", ("Honestly, since I really did not know what to do, I felt anger. Since I had to reiterate again and again the lesson for my learner with special needs, in addition to the regular learners. More so, I really did not have the idea what to do. And so, I felt so angry in this kind of classroom setting"), KI-6

Negative response to inclusive setting was also confirmed by more participants.

"Sa pagsugod, nagduha-duha ko basi mukalit siya ug tantrums. Hilom-hilom lang unya diay to naay probelma. Makahadlok pud." ("At first, I was so hesitant because I thought he might have tantrums. Maybe he was just silent but maybe inside he has inner problems, it was fearful."), KI-1

"Na-stress ko tibuok tuig kay isa nga factor wala ko'y alam. Feeling nako gisayang nako ang whole yeay nga naa siya sa akong klase." ("I was stressed the whole year because one of the major factors was I had no experience. I felt I wasted the whole school year that he was in my class."), KI-2

"Makalibog jud. Gitagaan ko'g stress kay di man ko kabalo unsaon pagdungan ug handle nila nga combination sa regular ug special." ("Very confusing. It gave me stress because I did not know what to do how to handle a class with a combination of learners and special child."), KI-5

Keenly delving into the responses, majority of the participants negatively considered handling a large class with additional learners with special needs. Most of them told that they could not concentrate focusing in teaching with diverse and different group with extremely different conditions and cases. One of the participants expressed her difficulty. KI-3 was handling a regular homogeneous class with fast learners. Mainstreamed in her class was a learner with Learning Disability (LD). In this class, extreme cases were observed. She expressed her sentiments as she quoted:

“Kani nga classroom setting lisod jud para sa akoo. Kay di ka ka-focus sa imong lesson. FL class man akoo unya LD siya. Although isa lang na ka bata pero dako siya ug factor nga makadistract siya sa lesson kay mutukar siya naa siyay times mutantrums siya. Sa first grading, maayo na kaayo akong lesson, tingala nalang ko naay nibuto, nagapanumbag siya, manluwa siya. Challenge jud kaayo siya sa pagpanudlo nako. Tanang pag-ampo ako ng gibuhat.” (“This kind of classroom setting was really hard for me to handle. He may be only one in class but it was a big factor because I considered him as a distraction every time his tantrums were triggered. During the first grading, I expected that my lesson ran smoothly, suddenly, I heard one of his seatmates crying because he was hit by... He was really one of the greatest challenges in my career. I have said all prayers just for him.”), KI-3

Another participant expressed her dislike in this inclusive classroom setting. She comprehensively pointed out her stand:

“Honestly, di nako siya type kay kung naay special nga bata with special needs, dapat lahion jud kay di jud sila mahatagan ug pansin kung naa siya sa regular class. Kay kanang learner with special needs di man na sila nagaafter nga makagrado. Kay ang regular, nagaafter ta nga makagrado ug asa siya sunod nga section ibutang, whereas sila, hulat lang tas ilang development. Siguro mam tungod sa naa koy sayings nga kanunay nako ginabutang sa akong kasingkasing nga “A loving teacher diay makes a classroom nga ang mga bata feel at home. Siguro pud sa akong motherly nga pagtudlo sa ilaha, nacater nako akong regular, at the same time, nacater nako akong special nga bata.” (“I honesty do not like this classroom setting because I always `believed that learners with special needs should be separated from regular learners because he could not be given proper and special attention if combined within a regular class. In a regular class, teachers are looking after the academic improvement of learners, whereas, an LSEN has different phasing. We need to wait for their development by the time they are ready.”), KI-5

Key Informant Interview 3 revealed that she had not exerted much dedication in educating the LSEN and planned to reject the child for the next school year, being afraid of handling the child again for another year.

“Wala kaayo ko nag-exert ug effort. Human isa ka tuig, happy na lang ko nga humana. Nag-suggest ko sa Sped teacher nga di na siya ibalik nako. Ibutang siya dapat sa non-gaded.” (“I have not exerted much effort. After one year, I was happy that the year ended. I suggested to the Sped teacher not to let the child go back to me. He must be placed in the non-graded.”), KI- 3

Similarly, Carroll's study (2003) on the views of Australian regular teachers reflected the negative attitude of informants on inclusion. Teacher's attitude clearly is one of the important factors to be considered before the actual implementation of inclusion. Their attitude is a contributing factor to its success or failure. If teachers do not have optimistic attitude towards children with special educational needs, meaningful education for them is far-fetched.

Resources. Among the most striking challenges of key informants is the lack of knowledge in formulating activities that will suit the LSENs needs. One key informant revealed how struggling it was to cater the need in providing appropriate resources for both her LSENs and regular learners:

“Challenge sa ako mangita ug activities nga haum sa iyang cognitive abilities. Naa pakoy mga regular. So, challenge sa ako mangita ug activities nga challenging nga i-work niya sa school.” (“It was a challenge for me to find activities that will suit his cognitive abilities. I also had my regular learners. So, the challenge was to find activities that are challenging for him to work on in school.”), KI-1

Key informant 2 affirmed the previous statement as she said:

“Lisod kaayo mangita ug resources ihatag sa iyaha.” (“It was a big problem for me to find what resources to provide him.”), KI-3

More key informants confirmed the accounts of the abovementioned informants:

“Lisod maghimo ug worksheets nga unique para lang sa iyaha.” (“I was so difficult to make worksheets unique for him”), KI-5

“Libog ang pagprepare sa activities, ang instructional materials pud”. (“I was confused in preparing the activities... the instructional materials as well”), KI-6

The above-mentioned experience of the participants aligns with the similar findings in the Report on Special Needs Education: Appraisal Exercise by the Ministry of Education in Kenya (2003). The findings in the report revealed that most schools lacked necessary teaching-learning resource materials and did not offer orientation and staff development opportunities to regular teachers. It was concluded that the effectiveness of inclusion was hampered by insufficient teaching-learning resource materials and poor staffing.

Moreover, studies of Santoli et. al (2008) demanded for the professional development trainings on inclusion for general education faculty. Barriers and challenges in inclusion can be holistically addressed if teachers, themselves, are equipped with the necessary preparations in implementing inclusion. Concrete, specific and on-going special education trainings must be accorded to receiving teachers. Not only does this addressed teacher problem but most significantly, it can affect teacher success in teaching inclusive classrooms.

Parent Support. In terms of parent's attitude, participants were also asked about the reaction of the parents, both of the LSENs' and of the regular learners', towards inclusion of their LSEN in the regular classes. Majority of them responded that their parents positively accepted the classroom set up of mixing their LSENs together with regular peers in a regular classroom setting. Their responses were:

"Wala may reklamo sa parents. Pasalamat pa gani sila." ("There were no complaints of parents. They were even very thankful"), KI-1

"Murag..wala ma'y nagreklamo nga parent sa akong special sa pag-mix sa iyaha." ("I think... there were no complaints by parents of my child with special needs against the mixture."), KI-2

"Wala man nuoy negative reaction ang parents sa bata nga naa siya sa akong regular class." ("I have not received any negative reactions of parents of special child placing her in the regular class."), KI-5

Participants' accounts aligned with the result of a qualitative study for teachers by Elzein (2009) wherein 15 parents were examined regarding their attitude toward mainstreaming children with special needs into regular private elementary schools in Sidon-Lebanon. In majority, the participants showed positive attitude towards the various aspects of inclusion, types and levels of inclusion.

Among the reactions of parents towards inclusion discussed, one came out differently. One of the participants revealed an incident where one of the parents of her regular learners expressed negative thoughts about placing the LSEN with the regular peers. She quoted:

"Yes, naa koy parent nga niingon nganong isagol man na mam nga buang-buang man na, wala man nay buot. Concern siya para sa iyang anak ". ("Yes, I had a parent who asked why should that child be mixed in this class, that child is insane, no manners at all. She has concern for her own child."), KI-6

With regards to parent attitude on inclusion, most studies in the field of research are roaming around the attitude of parents of learners with special needs (LSENs) placing their child in the regular class. But limited studies focused on the reactions of parents of regular learners. The scenario revealed by the participant mentioned above was somewhat threatening.

Leyser and Kirk (2004) suggested that parents should develop positive attitude towards mainstreaming their LSENs in the regular classroom setting in order to promote a least-restrictive environment for them. Furthermore, the findings of Bennett and Gallagher's study recommended that parent support must be intensified for a successful inclusive setting for diverse learners.

Dash (2018) concluded from the major findings in her study that some of the greatest barriers related to inclusion in education are negative attitudes. Many people are not prepared to interact with people with disabilities. Often, they are the object of ridicule or

outright ostracism in school and community. As with society in general, it is important that consistent and strong advocacy must be given to them considering that negative attitudes and stereotypes are often caused by a lack of knowledge, understanding, and acceptance of persons with disabilities and LSEs in general.

Administrative Support. All forms of support from school administrators and leaders are crucial to the success of inclusion in schools. But teachers' real experiences were disputable to this statement. Teachers, with hesitation to reveal the actual scenarios in school, divulged that despite their efforts to implement inclusive education, they were not compensated with the necessary support they should have been entitled and privileged to receive. Key informant interview quoted the following:

“Sa una pagsugod ug Sped Center sa school, ang principal nagahatag sa amoa ug materials pero karon, wala na, pati trainings.” (“During the early years of the school’s becoming a SpEd Center, the principal was supportive in providing us materials but for now, there were none, even the trainings.”), KI-1

“Honestly? So far, wala naman koy nadawat in any form of support sa principal oi.” (“Honestly? So far, I haven’t received any form of support from the principal”), KI-2

“Sa principal? Wala man. Wala man koy nadawat jud.” (“From the principal? There was none. I haven’t received any at all.”), KI-3

The accounts revealed by the key informants were supported by the Sped teacher and a regular co-teacher of the key informants in a short yet significant interview with them. The Sped teacher recounted:

“Actually, sa pagsugod sa pagka Sped Center jud sa school, okay man, Kompleto pa to ug mga materials ginahatag sa amoa. Pero kadugayan na, katong time na giisa na ang Sped fund sa MOOE, wala naman. Mas lahi na ang priority. Tibuok school na ang mas prioritize. So wala jud training nahitabo” (“Actually, during the early years of the implementation of the school as a SpEd Center, it was good. We were given complete set of materials. But as the years passed, by the time SpEd fund was merged with MOOEs, there was no more support. The school had different priorities. More priority was given to the entire school. There was really no training at all.”)

Similar statement was also given importance by a regular co-teacher of the key informants. She mentioned:

“Dili na priority ang mga SpEd kay ang tibuok school naman jud kay giisa naman ang MOOE. Mas daghan ug needs ang tibuok school nga dapat tagdon” (“SpEd is not given much priority. Priority is given to the whole school because of merging of MOOE (Maintenance and Other

Operating Expenses). The entire school has various needs that needs to be addressed.”)

These parallel narratives confirmed by other personnel in school clearly showed the critical and alarming condition of Special education in the actual field, leaving the regular education teachers helpless in implementing inclusive education practices. Indeed, this is a real scenario that calls for positive response from proper authorities.

The aforementioned accounts contradictorily tantamount to the ideal concepts that inclusive education should have been implemented. As emphasized in the recommendations presented in the study by Omapoy and Zerrudo (2019) conducted to different principals, for inclusion to be effective, managerial interventions must be contributed by principals to their teachers. One intervention that is closely linked in this study is for principals to provide administrative support in any forms to their teachers such as capability building trainings on inclusive education for teachers and strengthening of instructional leadership.

The positive relationship of administrative support to success of inclusion was commonly suggested in much of the research (Siegel, 1992; Barnett & Monda-Amaya, 1998; Cook et. al. 1999; Villa, Thousand, Nevin & Liston, 2005; Santoli, Sachs, Romey & McClurg, 2008). It is but disappointing to note that informants experience challenges related to lack of administrative support.

The above-mentioned accounts of the key informants sum up the different challenges and problems they encountered in implementing inclusive education. The findings on these problems were also proven and existent in the study of Gerber (2011). Among the enumerated challenges of inclusive education at elementary level in Gerber's study are lack of confidence of teachers to teach in inclusive settings, lack of training given to teachers how to teach in the inclusive education, no feedback from supervising officers have been provided about what the teachers are doing, curriculum is not adapted to the needs of special needs children. It was also stated that a classroom teacher is expected to select educational methodology to best suit each student.

Overcoming Challenges in Inclusive Education

To dig deeper into the teachers' experiences in implementing inclusive education for students with special needs, the researchers explore the teachers' challenges and how they overcame them to provide for the special needs of the students. This study found the overarching themes related to this aspect: consultation from experienced teachers, support from co-teachers, reinforcement through research, gathering support from parents, teachers' extra care and attention to LSENs, and teachers' utilization of personal resources.

Consultation from Experienced Teachers. Teachers are resourcefulness in many ways. Bombarded with negative challenges towards implementing inclusion, teachers find ways to suffice the lack of technical support they could get from others. As revealed by participants, they outsource information about inclusion and generally,

special education and sought help on different forms from reliable and experienced co-teachers particularly the Special Education teachers of their school. Participants revealed:

“Nangutana ko ug ideas sa akong mga kauban nga teachers unsa akong buhaton.” (“I asked and sought ideas from my co-teachers on what I will do”), KI-1

“Nag-interview ko sa among Sped teacher, nangutana ko bahin sa among bata nga gimainstream ug sa background niya para makabalo ko unsaon siya paghandle.” (“I interviewed Sped teacher, asked prior knowledge about mainstreamed learners and asked background of the special so I would know how to handle him”)., KI-2

More key informants confirmed the accounts when they said:

“Maliban sa nagreseach ko, nangutana pud ko sa akong mga kauban nga teacher, especially katong mga hawd na jud pareha sa mga Sped teachers.” (“So aside from doing research, I also asked my fellow teachers, especially the experienced ones such as the Sped teachers”)., KI-4

“Nagapangayo pud kog tabang sa akong mga co-teachers.” (“I also seek the help of my co-teachers”), KI-5

The participants' accounts were supported by the responses of one of experienced teacher in Special Education in the school. The SpEd teacher (SPED) upheld the statements of the participants that most of them approached and asked her for some queries and doubts about their LSEs.

“Oo, tinuod. Si Ma’am (KI-2) nangutana sa akoo about sa bata unya kay nakahandle man ko ana sa una, gisharean nako siya’g mga ideas unsay dapat anang bataa.” (“Yes. It’s true. Ma’am (KI-2) asked me about the child and since I handled him before, I shared to her some ideas in what to do with that child”), SpEd Teacher

“Si Ma’am (KI-4) nakig-istorya pud na siya about kang... pud iyang ginapangutana. Tabangan pud nako.” (“Ma’am (KI-4) talked to me about..., I answered her based on my previous experience with the child.”), SpEd teacher

Others also sought help from nearby Sped schools just to ease the uncertainty of the strategies they claimed to be as the right way of implementing inclusive practices.

“Actually, naabot ko sa laing skwelahan para lang makakuha ug idea unsaon. Sonehow, nakatabang man pud.” (“Actually, I went to other schools so I can gain ideas what should really be done. Somehow. it helped me in a way.”), KI-2

“Adto ko sa laing Sped schools ug nangutana sa mga teachers nga kaila nako.” (“I went to other SpEd schools and I asked the teachers whom I knew”), KI-6

Having experienced different challenges, non-trained teachers expressed their plea for the provision of adequate technical support through the conduct of meaningful and quality teacher trainings they deserve to receive. A participant suggested:

“Suggestion nako dapat naay jud trainings para sa amoang mga teachers nga nagadawat para makabalo pud mi kung tama ba o haum ba among ginabuhat.” (“I suggest Sped teachers should conduct trainings to us receiving teachers so we would know if what we were doing was right and appropriate.”), KI-2

With the support given by special education teachers, key informants revealed they were able to overcome challenges in lack of knowledge, lack of resources and training.

As suggested by Santoli et. al. (2008), one way of providing more expertise for general education is through collaboration or co-teaching. As similarly revealed by key informants in this study, general educators desire for more time to consult and plan with other general educators and special educators. Undoubtedly, it is imperative for a successful inclusion that teacher collaboration occurs.

Support from Co-Teachers. Faced with different kinds of challenges in implementing inclusion, non-trained teachers also needed emotional support in order to ease the so-called burden they experienced. Participants told the researcher about the help they got from colleagues:

“Support pud sila. Kani pud kauban nako nga Kinder naa pud siya’y special child, share share ra pud mi unsay mga gipangbuhat. Makat-on ra pud sa mga experience.” (“They supported me. Aside from them, I also had my partner in Kinder, she also has a special child so we shared ideas. We can learn from experience.”), KI-1

Co-teachers also supported Key informants 2 and 3 in terms of sharing their ideas and moral support. They unanimously shared:

“Supportive sa paghatag ug ideas.” (“Supportive in sharing ideas.”), KI-2
“Hatag silag moral support, mga advices unsay buhaton.” (“Moral support from co-teachers, advices on what to do help me to overcome the challenges.”), KI-3

“Nagatabang sila. Supportive kaayo kay nagahatag sila ug feedback sa akoo.” (“They were very helpful. They were so supportive in giving feedback.”), KI-4

Key informants 5 and 6 also revealed that there are co-teachers expressed sympathy over their experiences. They told:

“Nangumusta sila kung kamusta na ang bata. I also asked help from them.” (“They asked how was the child I received from them. I also seek the help from my co-teachers.”), KI-5

“Naluoy sila nako.” (“They pity me.”), KI-6

Through supportive channels, key informants were able to overcome the different challenges they had experienced. Key informants’ narratives as mentioned above were supported by their co-teachers. The Sped teacher affirmed:

“Tabangan pud nato unsay kailangan kay ang uban sa ilaha nidawat ra jud pud. Luoy pud oi! Kung unsay kaya i-share or matabang, tabang jud ta kay kauban ra gud na!” (“We should help them on what they need because most of them just accepted them (LSEs). I felt pity with them! What I can do to share and help, I should do it because they are my colleagues.”) Sped teacher

Support from their co-teachers were also provided. The co-teacher interviewed revealed:

“Kung ako pud naa sa ilang sitwasyon, di pud lalim noh. So, kung unsa man to akong natabang pareha kang Ma’am..., ginagmay nga pangutana nga giunsa na nimo, at least makahatag pud ug tambag gamay lang gud. Kay kung ako di man pud kabalo so tambag-tambag ra jud makaya nga support.” (“If I were in their situation, it would also be difficult for me. So, what I can do to help, just like to Ma’am (KI-3) petty questions on how she did it, at least, it helped a little advice because I, myself, am unaware on what to do. So, I just shared pieces of advice.”)

These confirmations of support system also emphasized how supportive co-teachers are with each other. Their little gestures of help were effective in alleviating the struggle that non-trained teachers felt in their endeavour to practice inclusive education in the best way they could. In the same way as expressed in the study of Santoli et. al (2008), regular educators practicing inclusion can be empowered through the support extended by co-teachers through collaborative teaching. It is inevitable that for general educators to support inclusion, teacher collaboration should be a prerequisite.

Reinforcement through Research. Innovative teachers as they are, participants also sought relevant information from the internet. For them, it helped information technology add a vast range of learning. Most of them divulged:

“Nagaresearch ko. Nakatabang ni madungagan akong kabalo sa special education pati inclusive education.” (“I did researches. This helped me gained more knowledge about special education as well as inclusive education”), KI-1

“Nagsearch ko Ma’am sa internet para makabalo unsay buhaton.” (“I researched Ma’am in the internet so I would know what to do.”), KI-2
“Usahay nagasearch kog ideas sa internet sa mga activities nga gamiton.”, (“Sometimes I seek ideas from the internet on the activities that I am going to use”), KI-5

Salend (2005) emphasized that effective inclusion requires reflective educators to examine their attitudes and beliefs. They are expected to differentiate their assessments, teaching methods and techniques, and classroom management practices to meet their learners’ needs. Similar to the versions narrated by key informants, it showed how resourceful they were in seeking means to provide themselves with knowledge and awareness about inclusive education in order to meet the demands of their diverse learners.

Gathering Support from Parents. When asked about any support from parents, participants disclosed how supportive their parents were:

“Supportive sila. Kung naa ko’y ihangyo bahin sa ilang anak, ila man pud iprovide.” (“In fairness, supportive pud. Ila ganing gipatutoran.”), KI-2

“They are supportive if I asked something, they will provide it.” (“In fairness, parents were so supportive. They even get a tutor for him”), KI-1

“Oo, supportive man sad.” (“Yes, they were also supportive.”), KI-3

“O. Pag naa kay assignment ginapabuhay, pag the following day naa jud answer. Pag naa pud activity sa school, ginapaapil pud nila as regular.” (“Yes, they were supportive parents. If I gave assignments, the next day, the child has answers. If there are activities in school, they let him join just like the regular learners.”), KI-5

“Supportive kaayo sila. Kung naa ko’y ihangyo para sa bata, ginahatag man pud nila dayon.” (“They’re so supportive. If I asked something for their child, they will provide it immediately”), KI-6

Gathering parental support revealed to be an important and essential factor for regular teachers in overcoming challenges encountered as revealed in their narratives. De Boer and Minnaert (2010) strongly stressed the important role played by parental attitudes in the process of implementing inclusive education. Positive attitudes of parents necessarily influenced the formation of their children’s attitudes towards an environment that supports the inclusion of LSEs. Salend (2005), also accentuated that parent attitude plays a vital role in the process of decision-making regarding inclusion. Thus, parents should give positive support towards inclusion for its success.

Teachers Showing Extra Care and Attention to LSEs. Participants, though untrained in inclusive education, made use of their innate love for children and passion for teaching to provide a least-restrictive environment for LSEs.

‘Ginapakita nako unsa ko kasweet sa iyaha, tungod ato, comfortable na siya sa akoo.’ (“I showed him how sweet I am to him, and with that, he felt comfortable and at ease with me”), KI-2

“Naa koy passion sa pagtudlo ug bata pareha nila nga maoy mas importante. Kung wala pa koy heart para nila, ang akong kalagot atong pagsugod, magpabilin gihapon sa akoo. Gisunod lang nako akong hart kay naluoy ko nila.” (“I have passion for teaching learners like them which is more important. If I do not have the heart, my feeling of anger before would still be here in my heart. I just followed my heart because I pity them.”), KI-6

“...ubanan nako siya pag wala pa iyang parents musundo. Extra attention jud ang ihatag sa iyaha” (“...accompanying him everytime his parents had not fetched him yet. So extra attention was really given to him.”), KI-1

Passion and love for teaching children revealed to be one of the most effective tools that regular teachers use to buffer themselves from the many challenges they encounter. This only showed that teachers’ commitment is unparalleled.

Teachers’ Utilization of Personal Resources. Insufficient funding, resources, and lack of support are some of the chief threats to the implementation of inclusion. It is reflected in the scarcity of resources like scarcity learning materials, resources, and the absence of support. Significantly, insufficient funding can hamper ongoing professional development that helps keep non-trained classroom teachers updated on the best practices of inclusion.

As resourceful teachers, key informants dealt with difficulties at their own level to ensure the effectiveness of their lessons. Left with no choice, key informants use their personal money to suffice the lack of materials and resources. Two of the participants revealed:

“Personal expenses jud nako. Usahay ang gamit sa ubang bata, magkuha ko i share sa iyaha.” (“It’s my personal expenses. Sometimes I asked form the things of his classmates and shared with him”), KI-6

“Gigamit nako akong sariling kwarta. Kailangan jud mangita ug laing paagi.” (“I use my own money. There’s really need to seek alternative. It takes personal willingness.”), KI-2

Informants’ accounts clearly manifested the resourcefulness of teachers in many forms. As Salend (2005) emphasized in his effective inclusion principle, educators need to reflect and to examine their attitudes and beliefs. To address the diverse needs for a successful inclusion, teachers maximized every means they can possibly do. As revealed in the accounts of informants, they were being flexible and resourceful which is driven by their positive outlook towards LSENs.

Success Stories

One of the principles discussed by Salend (2005) for inclusion to become successfully implemented is reflective practices and differentiated instruction. Effective inclusion demands educators who reflect and examine their attitudes. Furthermore, to have effective inclusive educators are expected to differentiate their assessment, the teaching methods and techniques they employ, and the classroom management they practice in order to meet each individual learner's needs and strengths, may they be regular or with special needs. To lead the classroom, a flexible, knowledgeable, thoughtful teacher must modify her/his teaching instructions and utilize her/his resources wisely to meet all learners' diverse needs and abilities.

Despite their lack of proper training, funding, and support, most participants in this study claimed to have achieved successful implementation of inclusion. They were generally fulfilled and satisfied in performing their duties and responsibilities as inclusive education teachers and most especially, helping the LSEs develop themselves in different aspects and phases. Success in inclusion was evident in the following factors: improvement in the learners' behavior and academic performance; achieving social maturity; satisfaction; positive impact and appeal for teacher training.

Improvement in the LSEs' Behavior and Performance. Though they lack inclusive education training, informants claimed to have witnessed the improvement in their LSEs. The responses of participants noted:

"Ang performances niya sa paperworks kay mas nitriple iyang kahawd."
(*"His performance in paperwork, his competence tripled."*), KI-1

"Naa puy improvement somehow. Kay dati sa English ug Filipino di siya kabalo jud. Niarang –arang siya sa Filipino. Naa siya'y development. Pero about sa kwarta, hawd siya especially magsukli sa tindahan. Kabalo na siya sa Math. Feeling nako, arang-arang siya sa Math."
(*"There is improvement somehow. Before in English and Filipino, he has really no knowledge at all. He improved in Filipino. He developed a lot. But in terms of money, he is very good in changing money in the store. He is now good in Math. I felt he improved in Math."*), KI-4

Nahawd siya sa Math. Kay higher level na ang grade one kumpara sa iyang level katong sa ipon pa siya sa SpEd class. Unya nakakuha man siya. Makacount na siya, makadd ug two-digit numbers with regroupings, makasubtract." (*"He became good in Math. Because grade one is higher level compared to his performance when he was in the SpEd class. And he can catch up. He can count, add two-digit numbers with regroupings. He can subtract."*), KI-5

"Karon makasulat na siya." (*"He can write now"*), KI-6

Despite the lack of training, the accounts revealed by regular teachers positively showed the success of regular teachers in their own contextualized implementation of inclusion. As Dakar and Senegal (2000) stressed, inclusive educators must ensure that children's diverse needs must be addressed equally. By applying such principles,

regular teachers were able to meet favorable results as manifested in the improvement of their LSEs. Indeed, including LSEs with regular peers was revealed to be effective in helping them improve and develop in several aspects.

Achieving social maturity. Key informants also shared how their LSEs improve in dealing and socializing with regular peers including their relationship with their teacher. They shared their stories from the time they improved up to the present.

“Strikto siya at first, karon kay open na kaayo siya pati sa akon magsige ug panawag sa cellphone mag-share ug basig unsa.” (“He was strict at first but now he was open to me. There are times he kept on calling me on my cellphone sharing something.”), KI-1

“Sa una nagatantrums siya. Pero karon love na siya sa iyang classmates. Nafeel nako nga naabot na siya sa iyang maturity stage.” (“Before, he kept on having tantrums. But now, his classmates love him. I felt he had reached his maturity stage”), KI-2

“Nagaparticipate na siya. Pati self-confidence niya, nadevelop na.” (“He is participative now. Even his self-confidence was developed.”), KI-6

Clearly, LSEs mainstreamed in regular classes manifested growth in emotional aspects as evident in the accounts of regular teachers. Dash (2018) supported the idea of inclusion. With this, LSEs can learn and improve despite any disabilities they may have. This principle was also upheld by the regular teachers. Because of regular teachers’ belief that LSEs can learn and armed with their passion and dedication to serve, LSEs were able to develop social maturity. Indeed, there is hope for LSEs contrary to what others seem to adversely prove.

Teachers’ Satisfaction. Having seen the positive results of the hard work they have exerted in contextualizing the lessons, activities, and strategies to cater to the diverse needs of their mixed learners, the majority of the key informants expressed their feelings of satisfaction and happiness.

“I’m so grateful sa iyang improvement.” (“I am so grateful with his improvement.”), KI-1

A feeling of happiness also filled Key informant 2. She expressed:

“Siyempre happy nga naay improvement. Makainspire pud nga naa diay mga lain laing klase sa mga bata nga naa diay mga ing ana nga murag wala lang regular pero naa jud diay mga ing ana nga bata.” (“Happy that there is improvement in him. It was inspiring to know that there are cases of LSEs that we thought as regular but with special needs.”), KI-4

Another positive regard was expressed by Key informant 5. She revealed her feelings of happiness:

“Makahappy makita nga naay improvement in a little way. Although sometimes taken for granted kay ang presumption, special rani. Walay ginaapas nga goal.” (“I felt happy to see his improvement in a little way. Although sometimes he was taken for granted because my presumption before was they are special. No need for goals to achieve.”), KI-5

Fulfillment was also experienced by Key informant 6 as she briefly expressed: *“Happy ug fulfilled kaayo ko kay wala gud koy alam jud. Ako-ako ra jud tp akong gibuhat. Salamat kaayo kay positive.” (“I am so happy and fulfilled because I really do not have enough knowledge. Everything I have done was based on my own initiative. I am so thankful that it came out positively”), KI-6*

Teacher satisfaction is essentially one of the factors in a successful inclusion. Similar studies by Whitaker (2000), Brownell, Sindelar, Kieley, and Danielson (2010), and Berry and Gravelle (2013) emphasized that teacher satisfaction can have an impact on the quality of the LSEs receive. Teachers who were resourceful had a wider network of support from available sources reported greater levels of satisfaction.

Positive Impact to Regular Teachers. Many challenges were encountered by key informants as they exerted different means in overcoming challenges in implementing inclusive education. As they were asked how this considerable improvement in their LSEs created an impact to their attitude towards teaching LSEs in an inclusive setting. Key informant 1 shared how her experiences in teaching LSEs shared her outlook towards them:

“Sa sugod kay naglisod ko kay naa pakoy regular daghag bata, naay pay special, unsaon na lang nako basi magkagubot ang room kung naa siya kay wala paman ko kabalo sa iyang abilities. Pero sa middle na, nakita nako nga wala diay problema kay naa pud diay special nga bata nga harmless.” (“At first, I have my regular, so many of tem, added with a special child, so what should I do because I thought that maybe this class will be in chaos if this child is with them because that was when I do not know his abilities. But in the middle of the school year, I have seen that there was no problem with special children that they are.”), KI-1

Key informant 3 also shared how inclusion changed her negative thinking towards handling LSEs.

“Ang akong mind kay medyo nakasabot na ang mga learners with special needs diay kay pwede diay makalearn despite sa ilang mga disability. Katong manageable lang pud. Depende ra jud sa case sa bata.” (“My mind now better comprehends about learners with special needs that they can also learn despite their disabilities. But those who are manageable. It really depends upon the child’s case.”), KI-3

Another key informant shared how inclusion inspired her to do better in her profession. She also became much eager to learn more strategies in order to better equip herself in teaching her LSEs as well as her regular learners. She positively explained:

“Mas nainspire pa ko nga magtudlo pa jud ug madungagan akong mga strategies para ang mga bata nga akong gihandle nga makalearn jud sila.” (“I was more inspired to teach more and to learn more strategies so that the children that I can handle can learn better.”), KI-4

Key informant 6 also had a positive change of attitude towards inclusion. He even developed love and understanding towards Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs). She noted:

“Sa una nasuko ko sa parent nga igo ra gihatag ang bata sa akua pero kadugay ang attitude nako sa iyaha, nalove na nako siya.” (“Before, I felt angry with the parent who just left her child under my care but eventually, my treatment with the child changed. I learned to love him.”), KI-6

With the positive change of attitude towards LSEs, key informants revealed how inclusion created an impact, not only on their LSEs, but most importantly, on themselves as educators. The success of inclusion ranges far beyond what regular teachers expect. Key informants were also asked if they would encourage others who desire to practice inclusion even without training. Despite their remarkable success, the majority of them preferred to have attended teacher training to equip themselves in the appropriate implementation and practice of inclusion. She explained:

“Okay lang nakaexperience sila naa silay special nga bata pero dapat naa jud training. Naa jud background” (“Its’ okay to experience handling special children but there should be training.”), KI-1

Similar impressions were also expressed by the key informant 2. She emphasized the importance of teacher training for a teacher to equip oneself with knowledge and understanding about inclusion. She emphasized her stand:

“Dapat naa jud training kay sa training, makakuha kag strategy, unsay set up paghandle ana nga bata. At least madungagan ang learning.” (“There should be training because it is where we get strategies, the set-up to handle this learners. At least there is additional learning.”), KI-2

Moreover, Key informant 3 expressed the value of teacher orientation and awareness in order to fully understand LSEs as well as inclusion. She firmly and strongly defended her stand:

“Dili oi. Dili jud kay ang hunahuna sa teacher di man gud kasabot anang mga bataa kay wala man sila naorient pareha sa akua sa una wala ko kabalo nga ing ana diay ng mga bataa. Mas nindot jud naay training tapos depende gihapon sa teacher kung willing siya kay iorient man na sa training kung ing ana sila.” (“Really not. The teacher cannot really understand this kind of learners because she was not oriented just like me before I did not know about these children. It is better to have trainings but it still depends upon the willingness of the teacher because it is in training that they will be oriented about these learners”), KI-3

Key informant 4 also affirmed her perspective in handling inclusion even without proper training. She also gave suggestions for teachers in seeking means of equipping oneself. She suggested:

“Pero mas maayo jud nga naay training para mas makabalo pa siya sa mga klase sa bata. Kung wala may mahatag nga training, ang buhaton pwede mueskwela. So, mas maayo pud iopen sa principal nga dapat naay para ing ani nga training.” (“It is better to undergo trainings so one can learn about different types of learners. If there are no trainings, one can go schooling in graduate studies. It is also good to be open to the principal that there should be training for this matter”), KI-4

Furthermore, key informants 5 and 6 also reiterated the effectiveness of teacher training in handling a mixture of diverse learners in one classroom set-up. They unanimously shared:

“No. Kay at least unta man lang kung mudawat ka ug learners with special needs dapat kabalo ka mubalance unsaon sila paghandle sabay-sabay tanan.” (“No. At least, if a teacher accepts a learner in her class, she knows how to handle different groups of learners at the same time”), KI-5

“...Pero iprefer nako mas nindot jud ug naay training para jud pud 100% kabalo ang maestra unsa iyang buhaton para dili pud hanaw.” (“...I preferred to have trainings so that 100 %, the teacher knows what to do with her diverse groups of learners.”), KI-6

In summarizing an extensive review of related studies, the same accounts of regular teachers expressed the need for ongoing training (Van Reusen et al., 2001; Santoli, Sachs, Romey, & McClurg, 2008). Furthermore, Bargerhuff and Wheatley's study asserted the empowerment of regular school teachers in accommodating LSEs in order to promote successful inclusion. Therefore, it is imperative that the provision of concrete, functional, and ongoing teacher training in inclusive education must be given much priority by the schools. Moreover, for regular education teachers, implementation of inclusion can be best practiced if they are equipped with the skills and expertise to handle learners with diverse needs and severity.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, the study revealed that despite a lack of formal training, regular teachers were able to implement inclusive education. Regular teachers experienced different challenges in implementing inclusive education. Despite their lack of training, regular teachers could overcome the different challenges through their own coping mechanisms and had a hard time implementing inclusive education with its implementation at present, considering mainly the lack of training and lack of institutional and operational support. Despite a lack of training in inclusive education, regular teachers were still able to experience success, as apparent in the improvement of their LSEs. Despite the evident success, regular teachers still plea for the provision of teacher training in inclusive education, knowing that this could make them more equipped with knowledge about the proper implementation of inclusive education rather than their own contextualized way.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, school administrators should design and conduct functional teacher training programs that promote positive attitudes and offer meaningful experiences for all teachers, untrained and newly-hired regular teachers including school administrators to enhance awareness and knowledge on inclusive education and special education in a broader sense. This move will give assurance to teachers that they will become adequately prepared for the task of educating all students within the regular education classroom. Parents of LSEs may also be invited for this purpose.

Provide the regular teachers with the appropriate and definitive teachers' guide and learners' materials that will cater to both the regular learners and LSEs purposely for the implementation of inclusive education. Instructional and manipulative materials should also be provided to cater to the diverse needs of regular learners and LSEs. Institutional and operational support in any form: physical, mental, emotional, and financial support should be provided by the department and the school administrators not only to Special Education teachers but also to the regular receiving teachers.

Physical support such as more spacious classrooms to cater to the large size of classes should be provided. Mental and emotional support such as stress management activities for teachers must also be provided. Allocating funds and financial support for instructional materials and manipulative materials must be given to teachers.

Schools must tap these regular teachers as resource persons to share their successful cases and best practices. Regular teachers should seek professional growth and advancement through active participation in seminars, training, and enrolling themselves in courses in special education as well as inclusive education so that they may be equipped with the skills to handle diverse learners since inclusion and "education for all" is inevitably the current trend in the school climate nowadays.

Moreover, continuing professional development is essential to maintaining the quality of education for all in our schools, public and private. The research findings in this study could assist the Education management personnel, planners, and policymakers in enhancing integration programs and augmenting orientation and staff development opportunities for non-trained teachers. More research on inclusive education curricula may be conducted to have more in-depth descriptions of the programs, especially for receiving teachers with a greater number of learners in a class.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers upheld the ethical principles by following ethical guidelines throughout this study. From the outset of the series of interviews, these guidelines ranged from undergoing approval processes before starting the research and conducting interviews, careful considerations were taken to ensure that the participants were kept completely anonymous in the research, and the interviews were held confidential to maintain the objectivity of the study and to keep the identities of the participants of this study completely anonymous thus maintaining their rights. Before data gathering commenced, the participants were given an informed consent letter to make them aware of their participation. Contents of the informed consent involved the rationale of the study, the activities conducted, and the general questions that were asked to obtain the information necessary to answer the study questions. The participants were informed that they would be asked a series of open-ended questions in one-on-one interviews, which were recorded. It was emphasized to the participants that their participation was highly voluntary, and they have the right to withdraw their consent or discontinue participation at any time without penalty or loss of benefits to which they are otherwise entitled. Likewise, they had the right to refuse to answer questions that they felt were stressful and that might embarrass them. They were also told that there would be minimal risks in participating in the study but that they could benefit more since they would be helping improve the programs for the teachers in the institution. Participation was also confidential since pseudonyms were assigned to them instead of their names to ensure privacy. In the consent, the researcher gave her contact details and email address so they could reach her if they had queries, hesitations, or concerns about the study. Finally, participants were asked to affix their signatures to signify their consent and voluntary participation in the study.

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